

Design and Implementation of PWM Signal Generator

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Abstract— This document gives information regarding implementation of PWM Signal Generator. The concept of the PWM Signal is nothing new. PWM Signal is a very commonly used signal in digital electronics for control circuitry. The design of PWM Signal Generator is based on using PIC16F877A on a breadboard. This system will generate PWM Signal from the PIC MCU which has a special module called Compare Capture module (CCP) which can be used to generate PWM signals. The generated PWM signal is of 5 kHz with a variable duty cycle from 0% to 100%.

Keywords— PIC PIC16F877A, Resistor, Capacitor, Breadboard, Potentiometer, CCP1CON Register.

I. INTRODUCTION

Some machines only require partial or variable power. Full power is not required. Previously, controlling was done by the use of a rheostat which was connected in series with the motor in order to adjust amount of current flowing through the motor. It was quite inefficient because power was wasted as heat in the resistor element of the rheostat. It was tolerable though because the total power was low. The rheostat was one of methods of controlling power but a low cost and efficient power adjustment method was needed. This mechanism also required to drive motors for fans, pumps and robotic servos, and needed to be compact enough to interface with lamp dimmers. PWM emerged as a solution for this complicated problem [1].

PWM is often used for controlling servomechanism. In the field of telecommunications, PWM is a form of signal modulation. Here the widths of the pulses correspond to specific data values encoded and decoded at the both ends. PWM can be used to control the amount of power delivered to a load without losses which would have resulted via linear power delivered by resistive means [2]. The power drawn by the load and energy delivered to the load is discontinuous. High frequency PWM power control systems can be produced with semiconductor switches. PWM can also be used in efficient voltage regulators. By switching voltage to the load with proper duty cycle, the output will approximate a voltage at the desired level. PWM techniques can be used to make some indicator blink softly. The light will slowly transition from

dark to full intensity, and vice versa. Then it repeats the whole cycle [3].

The design of PWM Signal generator is based on microcontroller PIC16F877A IC on a breadboard. PWM Signal will be generated from the PIC MCU which has a special module called Compare Capture module (CCP). This system will detect PWM signal which has many applications. The generated PWM Signal can be used as required. [4].

II. METHODOLOGY

The implementation of this project involves the use of the PIC16F877A microcontroller IC to generate a PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signal, with a controllable duty cycle ranging from 0% to 100% at a fixed frequency of 5 kHz. This variable duty cycle is achieved by reading an analog input from a potentiometer, which is connected to the PIC's ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter) module. The analog voltage input, which ranges from 0 to 5V, is digitized by the ADC, yielding a mapped digital value between 0 and 1024. This digital value is then used to modify the PWM signal's duty cycle dynamically, where 0 corresponds to a 0% duty cycle and 1024 corresponds to a 100% duty cycle.

To stabilize the PWM output, the project incorporates a 20 MHz crystal oscillator in parallel resonance with two 22 pF capacitors. This configuration is crucial for maintaining optimal current at the desired frequency, ensuring stable PWM signal generation. The parallel resonance setup enables maximum current at the resonant frequency, providing stability essential for applications requiring precise frequency control. This arrangement supports the generation of a reliable and stable PWM output that can be adjusted in real-time through the potentiometer, making the system suitable for a variety of applications, such as motor control, LED dimming, and other analog control scenarios. By leveraging the PIC16F877A's capabilities and the precision provided by the crystal oscillator setup, the methodology facilitates accurate duty cycle modulation through simple and efficient analog-to-digital conversion, with real-time adjustments available via the potentiometer.

$$\text{Resonant Frequency} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{\frac{1}{LC} - \frac{R^2}{L^2}}} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

III. CIRCUIT DESIGN

The implementation of this PWM signal generator is carried out on a breadboard. The core components include the PIC16F877A IC, a 1k potentiometer, a 20 MHz crystal oscillator, and various supporting components like resistors and capacitors. The crystal oscillator, along with 22 pF capacitors, is connected to the PIC MCU, ensuring precise timing for PWM signal generation. The potentiometer is wired to the ADC input of the PIC to read the variable voltage, which in turn adjusts the duty cycle. The output PWM signal can be observed on an LED, which will vary in brightness based on the duty cycle. A 9V power supply is used to power the entire circuit, and breadboard connectors help organize the connections on the breadboard for testing and experimentation.

Fig. 1. PWM Signal Generator circuit diagram

IV. ADC MAPPING

A. PWM Signal Generation: The PWM signal is generated using the CCP (Compare Capture PWM) module in the PIC16F877A microcontroller. A 40-pin microcontroller is utilized in this project, as it includes the necessary CCP module, which is absent in the 28-pin version. The PWM signal is configured with a 10-bit resolution, where a digital value of 0 corresponds to a 0% duty cycle, and a value of 1024 (2^{10}) represents a 100% duty cycle. Due to the presence of two CCP modules (CCP1 and CCP2), two separate PWM signals can be generated simultaneously on pins 17 and 16, respectively. In this setup, the PWM signal is produced on pin 17 [5].

B. Analog-to-Digital Conversion and Duty Cycle Variation:

The microcontroller reads an analog voltage (0-5V) from a potentiometer, which is then mapped to a digital value range of 0-1024 via the ADC module. A PWM signal with a frequency of 5 kHz is generated, and the duty cycle is adjusted based on the input voltage. Specifically, an ADC reading of 0 maps to a 0% duty cycle, while 1024 maps to a 100% duty cycle. The CCP module is configured as follows to enable PWM operation:

- The PWM period is set by writing the desired value to the PR2 register.
- The duty cycle is adjusted by setting the CCP1L register and the CCP1CON<5:4> bits.
- The CCP1 pin is designated as an output by clearing the TRISC<2> bit.
- Timer2 is activated, and the TMR2 prescale value is set in the T2CON register.
- The CCP1 module is then configured to operate in PWM mode.

C. Frequency Setting and Duty Cycle Calculation:

The PWM frequency is established by writing an appropriate value to the PR2 register, calculated using the formula:

The target PWM frequency is set to 5 kHz by assigning $PWM_freq = 5000$. The duty cycle is determined by the function:

$$PR_2 = \frac{XTAL_FREQ}{PWM_FREQ \times 4 \times TMR2PRESCALE} - 1$$

These steps ensure the generation of a stable PWM signal, with the duty cycle dynamically controlled by the input from the potentiometer. Duty Cycle, D is

$$D = \frac{Float_Duty}{1023} \times \frac{XTAL_FREQ}{PWM_FREQ \times TMR2PRESCALE}$$

V. RESULT & ANALYSIS

The design of the PWM Signal Generator is implemented using the PIC16F877A microcontroller on a breadboard. This system generates a PWM signal utilizing the Compare Capture module integrated within the microcontroller. The frequency of the generated PWM signal is set at 5 kHz, with a duty cycle ranging from 0% to 100%. Below is the simulated circuit diagram used for generating the PWM signal:

Fig. 2. Simulated Circuit diagram

Fig. 3. Simulated Output of PWM signal

Fig. 4. Output for 100% pwm signal

VI. COST ANALYSIS

The total cost of the smart home project is ****670 BDT****, encompassing essential components such as the PIC16F877A microcontroller (300 BDT), passive components (70 BDT), and infrastructure (180 BDT). This cost-effective investment offers potential benefits like energy savings, increased property value, and enhanced convenience. Overall, the initial investment is justified by long-term financial and functional gains.

TABLE I. Cost analysis of PWM Generator

Component name	Description	Quantity	Price
PIC16F877A	40 pin micro controller	01	300 BDT
Resistor	10 K ohm	01	30 BDT
Capacitor	22 pF	02	20 BDT
LED	Light emitting Diode	01	20 BDT
Breadboard	Connection board	01	120 BDT
Wires	Connection wires	08	60 BDT
Potentiometer	1k potentiometer	01	30 BDT
Crystal Oscillator	20 Mhz Crystal Oscillator	01	30 BDT
Battery	9V Battery	01	60 BDT
		Total	670 BDT

VII. COMPETITIVE STUDY AND FUTURE SCOPE OF PWM SYSTEMS

The project utilizes a PIC microcontroller to generate clean PWM signals with variable duty cycles, distinguishing it from other signal generation methods. As advanced systems increasingly adopt PWM technology, the future scope of this project is significant. Applications include modern computer systems, where CPU fans can use PWM to adjust speed based on temperature. Additionally, demand for control circuitry is rising, with recent studies indicating that the PWM controllers market is projected to grow by 5.1% through 2032 [6].

VIII. APPLICATIONS

PWM signals are versatile tools used in various systems for efficient control and power management. Here are some key applications [7]:

- Servomechanism Control: Frequently used for precise movement control in servos.
- Voltage Regulation: Controls the voltage received by loads, enabling efficient power delivery with minimal losses.
- Efficient Voltage Regulators: Utilized in voltage regulation systems for stable output.
- Soft Blinking Indicators: PWM techniques create smooth, soft blinking effects in indicators.
- Lossless Power Delivery: Ensures efficient and lossless power transfer.
- Fan Speed Control: Replaces DC signals to adjust CPU and case fan speeds dynamically based on temperature conditions.

IX. CONCLUSION

The PWM signal generator system was successfully implemented using the PIC16F877A microcontroller, demonstrating its effectiveness in generating PWM signals. While the current design allows for adjustable duty cycles, there is significant potential for improvement, such as extending the range of the duty cycle for greater control. Furthermore, the system's adaptability enables it to be connected to various applications that require PWM signals, enhancing its utility in fields like servomechanism control and voltage regulation. Overall, the project lays a strong foundation for future enhancements and broader applications, promising valuable contributions to power management and control systems.

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